

**PLACE OF FIGURATIVE EXPRESSIONS IN VOCABULARY
AND LANGUAGE SYSTEM**

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Annotation: This article outlines to analyze the phonetic, lexical, morphological and syntactic features of Uzbek and Russian pictorial units and to reveal their semantic system relationships;

Key words: figurative words, exclamations, Image blocks, Picture units, human appearance

The systemic nature of the language manifests itself in two directions. At the first stage, systematization within the framework of one language level is assumed, and at the second stage, the unity and struggle of oppositions between language levels is shown, which is combined with the question of the unity of linguistic and non-linguistic factors.[1] "Linguistics, integrating different aspects of the language and studying it as a whole, as a system, was formed in the 20s of our century and became known as system-structural linguistics." [2] Recognizing the advantages of systems linguistics, it is necessary to objectively recognize and recognize the achievements of other approaches, including the traditional school of linguistics. After all, any innovation is based on an earlier, relatively incorrect phenomenon, the task of innovation is to relatively eliminate these shortcomings, to some extent to make up for them. However, the problem cannot be solved perfectly; this relative solution to the problem creates new problems. Indeed, this is the logic of the viability of science and practice. It is known that according to the grammatical structure, languages are divided into four types: disjunctive, agglutinative, incorporative and inflectional languages. [3] This relativity lies in the fact that the language fully and without exception corresponds to its classification base. Because, for example, agglutinative languages are not free from inflection and inflection, and inflectional languages are not free from features of other types. In general, inflectional language families are ranked according to the degree of mutual inflection, while agglutinative languages are ranked according to the degree of agglutination - this feature is more common in one language and less common in another. The axiomatic nature of this is substantiated by the relativity of the morphological classification of languages. In the Uzbek language belonging to the second group, it can be said that the root does not undergo changes (!) when the word receives various forms and derivational suffixes, but its meaning relatively changes when one or more suffixes are added. to the base of the word. The morphological

system of such languages differs from other types in its consistency, the organic proximity of the components of the system, and their multiplicity. It has recently been observed that there are no more than 150 grammatical forms of the verb in English, and more than 100,000 in Uzbek, and the incredible hypothesis has been put forward that there are more than 1 million grammatical forms of (one) verb in the Uzbek language. [4] When studying the Uzbek language as a system, it is important not to ignore even the smallest language units. Because in this case, each significant language unit carries in its semantic structure at least two of the meanings of the name, function and expression.

It can be said that figurative words serve to increase the level of expressiveness and emotionality of speech, if at all we evaluate languages with different constructions as a means of communication. The same semantic task parallelizes figurative units in languages with different constructions. However, determining the morphological position of figurative words in many languages remains problematic. It has been proven by linguists that figurative words cannot be recognized as an independent group of words. However, the inclusion of these means in the list of imitations, although not an independent category, cannot be considered one of the universal conclusions. It is worth saying that the level of occurrence of figurative units in speech is much higher than that of imitations, and although there are cases when they intersect with it, the volume goes beyond this category. This situation is typical for both oral and written speech, and this active accident further activates the question of the morphological identification of figurative words. "For a long time, imitation (including figurative units) and exclamations were studied together. Recently, they began to be divided into separate, unrelated lexico-semantic groups. From the point of view of science, imitation is relatively "old", but in linguistics they represent a newly formed group, and it is natural that the structure of this category has not yet been fully explored. From a linguistic point of view, when separating imitations from pronunciation, the next step is the need to separate imitations from figurative units. In the Uzbek language, the words in the following examples can be classified as imitations. For example: Юнус ота ўчоқни тозалаб, қозонни ўчоққа қўндирғон пайтда йигитлар ёнғоқ тагига етиб келдилар, тарс-турс қилдириб елкаларидаги кетмонларини ерга ташладилар. (А.Қодирий "Қуёш билан ҳам курашаман"); Бунга сайин қора қўнғиз мошин ичи яна бир қат қўрқинч ҳолга кирар, бир-бировининг пинжида нажот топадигандек сиқилишиб ўтирган аристонлар шамолга дош беролмай қарс-курс синган шох-шабадедек тинмай силтанар, қайси

бири“их”раб, бошқаси “мих”раб ёлбориш товуши чиқарарди.
(Ҳ.Дўстмуҳаммад “Ёлғиз”).

Figurative units are found in speech as follows. For example: Раҳматулла тўрда,
чуғурчуқдек чуғурлашган икки ўғилчаси икки ёнида, дастурхонда ҳил-ҳил
пишган таом, пойгакда — аллақандай баҳорий либосда ўн саккиз яшар
пайтидагидек очилиб кетган Нозимахон... (Ҳ.Султонов “Тўқчилик ва
йўқчилик”); Ўзи айтиб, ўзи маст бўлиб рақсга тушадиган, жойи келса,
таппа ерга ётиб оладиган, питир-питир ҳаракатлар қиладигани бор-ку,
ўшанинг худди ўзи. (О.Ҳожи “Ҳаваскор бедана”)

Historically, a variety of terms have been used to refer to imitations (including
figurative words). Plato proposed to unite these means under the term "mime",
and scientists began to use such terms as figurative words, imitative words,
figurative words, imitations and onomatopoeia.

“Due to the fact that imitative (as well as descriptive words) do not have the
features of classification and accentuation, most scientists studying Turkic
languages consider them as an invariable group of words, lexically and
grammatically these units are equated with exclamatory or idioms. However,
they are distinguished from these groups by a number of characteristics and
characteristics.[5] Of course, both the term " турланиш " and the term "
тусланиш " in this quote get in the way of the point. Because the type is a
general and syntactic event and is combined in part of a sentence. Such a
classification is incorrect, and following the Turkic schools of linguistics and
Uzbek linguistics, the conclusions on this issue are subject to clarification.
Because to say that figurative words do not have the property of inflection and
variation means to completely deny their obvious morphological origin. The
possibility of appearing as a sentence or phrase is associated with self-change.
There is another specific view that covers figurative words, including imitations
and exclamations. This point of view is directly related to the assumptions about
the origin of the language. Thinkers who connect the origin of language with
natural phenomena, such as Jean-Jacques Rousseau, who is considered the
founder of this view, reflecting on the origin of languages, say that “initially,
languages are lyrical and emotionally strong, later these languages become
relatively humanized and structured.” In his opinion, language is not a means of
expressing human perception, but a physiological ability that reflects his
feelings. The emotional person, seeking to express his feelings, did so by
"implanting" natural sounds and situations. As a result, these imitations settled
in our speech and began to designate new types of meanings. Before expressing

a concept, a person observed its realization in being and translated it into speech, based on his articulatory capabilities. This is how human speech is enriched. At first glance, this idea seems reasonable. However, two reasons are sufficient to justify the relative falsity of this hypothesis. For example, "if words really came from the properties of nature and phenomena, then all concepts and names would be the same in different languages, and the existence of different languages would be groundless." [6] Secondly, human speech is built around abstract concepts, and not only expresses tangible concepts. The source of their imitation and imitation cannot be natural or other phenomena. Although such an erroneous hypothesis, evaluating figurative words as a fundamental tool in the formation of language, increases the value of the object of study, this idea must be abandoned due to the lack of sufficient evidence to prove it and the scope of the study. critical conclusions that can be countered. "All languages - even languages that are very different from each other - are actually very close to each other. Their uniqueness is revealed only when compared with other languages. In particular, figurative words have the following phonetic features and structure in different system languages:

Phonetic and shaky parallels:

Image blocks can be paired;

The sound change is observed in the second part of the double image block;

Picture units have a smaller sound pattern than other words in all languages. They consist of one or two syllables;

Consonant layering in the composition of visual units is characteristic of all languages;

When creating a new word with the help of affixes, changes in the composition of the sound unit of the image are possible.

In addition, another aspect of figurative words determines their clear difference from other categories of words at the phonetic level. That is, unlike words belonging to other independent groups of words, figurative words contain unusual sound combinations. These unusual sound combinations belong to figurative words in almost all languages and in this respect are close to imitations.

Figurative words in all languages, regardless of the level of grammatical construction, poetics and expressiveness, express the following entities, which can be called the semantic etymology of figurative words:

Naming schemes of descriptive knowledge:

Image of a natural phenomenon;

Motion picture;

Image of natural state;

Image of facial expressions;

Image of human appearance;

Image of human character

Since figurative words are first learned separately from imitation, it is a good approach to leave the above table as an open system. The reason is that, as in all lexemes in which the expression scheme is leading, the meanings of portable words cannot be limited to a certain limited amount. Also, as can be seen from the above types of meaning, figurative words mean not only the impression of the phenomenon, but also the attitude of the speaker to the phenomenon. Both types of words can be called imaginary units. An open system retains the possibility of dividing figurative words expressing the speaker's attitude into new semantic groups not according to their source, but according to their negative or positive meaning. Basically, all words have a "texture", which can be called "divine" based on the idealistic theory of the emergence of language. Textual words such as those above correspond to such an idealistic idea and are fundamentally different from the imitations on which the materialistic idea is based. "The semantic and functional differences of figurative words in different languages constitute the national and cultural specificity of these means, it is necessary to carefully study these features in order to avoid communicative errors. According to etymological features, pictorial units can be given the following qualities. There are no proper words among figurative units. Figurative words in any language have a purely national etymology. The reason for this is that figurative words are first formed in vernacular. They will have the most convenient, understandable sound pattern for the speakers. These words, having taken a permanent place in oral speech, eventually begin to be used in written sources. Since the universal language is a source of figurative units, it is inappropriate to look for words of origin among them. Image units are a category, the semantic and sound shells of which, as well as grammatical indicators, are in constant change and movement. Therefore, if these units are grouped as a functional and semantic field, they can be recognized as a living and dynamic paradigm.

In conclusion, Visual aids are used in written and oral speech to increase the expressiveness, emotionality and expressiveness of the statement. In a literary

text, they are used to enhance melody, sonority and rhyme. In children's literature, these words can mean belittling, caressing.

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